

This is the psychedelic psychology of the week. What I know so far:

Moody Monday, the day of mirrors.

Nuclear Tuesday, of salt and sugar, and elemental colour in between, the day of fluctuations.

Wednesday is the day of work, the day of wobbles.

Thirsty Thursday, the day of drinks, the day of orbs.

Friday is the day of rest, and why would you rest you dope, I'd rather marry my bed, the day of strings.

Saturday is the day of MDMA in that mummery day mum approves, the day of waves.

Sunday is the day of LSD in that it should be the last saved day, the day of fields.

The quantum weirdness of the temporal week.